

PREVALENCE, KNOWLEDGE, AWARENESS, AND ATTITUDE ON E-CIGARETTES (ELECTRONIC CIGARETTES) AMONG SAINT MARY'S UNIVERSITY SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Prevalence, Knowledge, Awareness, and Attitude on E-Cigarettes (Electronic Cigarettes) among Saint Mary's University Senior High School Students

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Abstract

Electronic cigarettes (e-cigarettes) are becoming increasingly popular among adolescents, despite the lack of research on their long-term health effects. While general studies on adolescent e-cigarette use exist, research specifically focused on senior high school students' knowledge, awareness, and attitudes is limited. This study aimed to address this gap by determining the prevalence of e-cigarette use, knowledge, risk awareness, and attitudes among senior high school students at Saint Mary's University. A descriptive-comparative-correlational approach was employed, utilizing a survey questionnaire adapted from previous studies. The questionnaire included sections on demographics, prevalence of use, knowledge, awareness, and attitude, along with an open-ended question on perceived positive and negative effects of e-cigarette use. Data was collected from 400 students using a quota sampling method, ensuring representation from all academic strands. The study found a 51.5% e-cigarette use rate. While students demonstrated good overall knowledge of health risks, awareness of societal implications was moderate. Interestingly, students generally held negative attitudes towards e-cigarettes. However, awareness levels varied by grade level, and both sex and grade level influenced student attitudes. Additionally, there is a positive correlation between awareness and e-cigarette use. Students' perceptions were diverse, with some acknowledging positive effects like stress relief and others expressing concerns about addiction and health risks. These findings suggest a need for educational campaigns and curriculum integration that address knowledge gaps and combat misperceptions about e-cigarettes to deter adolescents from using them.

Keywords: *electronic cigarette, prevalence, knowledge, awareness, attitude*

Introduction

The use of electronic cigarettes has escalated among adolescents in the Philippines, becoming a growing public health concern. According to the Global Youth Tobacco Survey (GYTS) in the Philippines in 2019, 24.6% of Filipino youth aged 13–15 reported trying e-cigarettes. This represents a significant increase compared to previous years, such as 2015, when only 11.7% of youth reported having tried e-cigarettes. Moreover, an estimated 14.1% of said age group are current e-cigarette users (Jaminola III, 2022). The statistics reveal the urgent need for research and effective regulatory measures to address this issue. Particularly because nicotine can harm the developing adolescent brain, potentially leading to long-term consequences such as addiction, mood disorders, decreased attention, and learning capacity (Undo, 2022). Hence, there is a need to prevent and reduce youth access to e-cigarettes due to these potential harms.

E-cigarettes, also known as electronic cigarettes or vaping devices, are a type of electronic nicotine delivery system (ENDS) that are designed to deliver nicotine to the user in the form of an aerosol (American Cancer Society [ACS], 2022). These are battery-powered devices that heat a liquid (known as e-liquid or vape juice) containing nicotine, flavorings, and other chemicals to create an aerosol that is inhaled by the user. Many adolescents remain unaware of the potential health risks associated with their use, some of which include addiction, lung damage, organ damage, and other negative health outcomes (Cleveland Clinic [CC], 2022). Furthermore, research has shown that adolescents who use e-cigarettes are more likely to transition to traditional cigarette smoking and other tobacco products, which is particularly concerning given that cigarette smoking remains a leading cause of preventable death worldwide (Sokol & Feldman, 2021). Since adolescence is a period of significant physical, cognitive, and emotional development, young people are vulnerable to engaging in risky behaviors like using e-cigarettes.

In the Philippines, the government has taken steps to regulate e-cigarettes and address the concerning rise in their use among adolescents. Republic Act 11900, also known as "An Act Regulating the Packaging, Use, Sale, Distribution, and Advertisements of Electronic Nicotine and Non-Nicotine Delivery Systems and Heated Tobacco Products," was enacted on July 25, 2022. This law aims to provide guidelines for the proper regulation and control of e-cigarettes. Additionally, the Food and Drug Administration issued Administrative Order 2019-0007, which established guidelines for the registration and marketing of e-cigarettes and vaping devices. The order aims to ensure that these products are safe, of good quality, and not specifically targeted toward minors. "In the context of the newly passed law, individuals may have the impression that despite being legitimized and regulated, these products are safe and will not cause harm to their health" (Sese & Guillermo, 2023). Additionally, though marketed as a safer alternative to traditional tobacco products, these products have potential health risks in usage nonetheless (National Institute on Drug Abuse [NIDA], 2020).

Thus, to gain an understanding of why the youth are drawn to using e-cigarettes and how their accessibility contributes to it, it is vital to highlight both quantitative studies, such as studies on knowledge, attitudes, and practices, as well as qualitative and mixed method

studies because these offer insights that will provide important information for the development of prevention and intervention efforts (Sese & Guillermo, 2023).

Electronic Cigarettes (E-cigarettes)

Electronic cigarettes, or e-cigarettes, have become a popular alternative to traditional cigarettes, with many people using them as a smoking cessation aid or a way to reduce harm (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2023). However, e-cigarettes are not without risks, and there is growing evidence that they can have harmful effects on health. One of the major concerns with e-cigarettes is their effect on lung health. E-cigarette aerosols can contain harmful chemicals, including volatile organic compounds, heavy metals, and carcinogens (CDCP, 2023). These chemicals can cause damage to lung tissue and contribute to inflammation and respiratory problems, such as chronic bronchitis and asthma (Gotts et al., 2019).

Another area of concern is the cardiovascular system. E-cigarettes can cause increased heart rate, blood pressure, and narrowing and hardening of the arteries, all of which increase the risk of heart disease and stroke (Keith & Bhatnagar, 2021). The nicotine in e-cigarettes is primarily responsible for these effects, as it is a vasoconstrictor that can cause blood vessels to constrict and reduce blood flow.

In addition, e-cigarettes can also have harmful effects on the immune system. Studies have found that e-cigarette aerosols can suppress the immune system's response to infections and increase the risk of respiratory infections (Gotts et al., 2019). Furthermore, e-cigarette use has been associated with increased inflammation and oxidative stress in the body, which can contribute to a variety of health problems (Miyashita & Foley, 2020).

There are also concerns about the effects of e-cigarettes on brain development, particularly in young people. Nicotine, which is present in many e-cigarette products, is known to be addictive and can have harmful effects on the developing brain. Likewise, e-cigarette use is associated with a higher likelihood of future tobacco use and may serve as a gateway to traditional cigarette use (National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine [NASEM], 2018).

Furthermore, the safety of the chemicals used in e-cigarette flavorings is a concern. Many of these flavorings have not been adequately tested for safety when heated and inhaled, and some are toxic and can cause damage to lung cells (Marques et al., 2021; U.S. Food and Drug Administration [FDA], 2020).

Electronic Cigarettes (E-cigarettes) Use among Students

Several factors have been identified as important determinants of e-cigarette use among students, particularly adolescent students. Peer influence has been found to be a significant factor contributing to e-cigarette use among adolescents. Adolescents are more likely to initiate e-cigarette use if their peers are using e-cigarettes. Consequently, peer pressure has been identified as a key factor contributing to the escalation of e-cigarette use (Wang et al., 2022).

Perception of health benefits has also been identified as a potential factor influencing adolescents' e-cigarette use. Some adolescents may perceive e-cigarettes as a harmless alternative to traditional cigarettes. This perception can lead to increased e-cigarette use (Miech et al., 2019). However, research suggests that e-cigarettes can still pose health risks, including addiction to nicotine and respiratory problems (NASEM, 2018).

Marketing and advertising have also been identified as significant factors that can influence adolescents' decisions to use e-cigarettes. E-cigarette companies often market their products with attractive flavors, sleek designs, and messages. Studies have shown that adolescents who are exposed to e-cigarette advertising about e-cigarettes on social media are more likely to use e-cigarettes themselves (Vogel et al., 2021). Additionally, the use of flavored e-cigarettes has been identified as a factor that contributes to the appeal of e-cigarettes among adolescents (Soneji et al., 2019).

Moreover, mental health conditions, such as depression, anxiety, and attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), have been associated with increased e-cigarette use among adolescents. Adolescents with mental health conditions may use e-cigarettes as a coping mechanism, which may increase their risk of e-cigarette dependence (Riehm et al., 2019).

Accessibility is yet another issue in the Philippines, with 37.1% of the youth not being prevented from the purchase of said products either online or from street vendors, regardless of their age (Sese & Guillermo, 2023; Philippine Legislators' Committee on Population and Development [PLCPD], 2021). E-cigarettes are easily accessible in convenience stores, online platforms, and social settings. Online sales, coupled with inadequate age verification measures, make it easier for adolescents to obtain this product.

Knowledge on Electronic Cigarettes (E-cigarettes)

Knowledge is defined as "understanding of or information about a subject that you get by experience or study" (Cambridge, 2023). In the context of electronic cigarettes, knowledge pertains to the understanding of various aspects related to these devices. This includes knowledge about their components, functionality, usage guidelines, and potential health risks. Knowledge can be obtained through various means, such as reading scientific studies, researching reliable sources, or personal experiences with using or encountering electronic cigarettes.

Having knowledge about electronic cigarettes is crucial for individuals who use or are considering using them. It allows users to make informed decisions regarding their usage, helps them understand the potential risks and benefits, and enables them to navigate the rapidly evolving landscape of electronic cigarette products. Knowledge empowers users to choose suitable devices, understand proper usage techniques, and know the potential adverse effects, ultimately promoting responsible and safe use.

Several studies have shown a significant association between knowledge and electronic cigarette use. A study conducted by Kurdi et al. (2021) focused on youth and found that those who possessed greater knowledge of the potential harms associated with e-cigarette use were less likely to engage in their use. This implies that having in-depth knowledge of the harmful effects of e-cigarettes can serve as a deterrent to their usage among adolescents. In contrast, a study by Chudech, S. & Janmaimol, P. (2021) found that students with less knowledge about the harmful effects of electronic cigarettes were more likely to use them. This suggests that a lack of understanding or awareness about the potential risks associated with e-cigarettes can contribute to increased usage among young individuals. Similarly, another study identified a concerning trend among some adolescents who were attracted to flavored e-cigarettes despite having limited knowledge about the associated health risks (Pepper et al., 2016). Thus, factors such as appealing flavors and social influences may play a significant role in e-cigarette initiation, overshadowing the lack of understanding regarding potential harms. These findings highlight the crucial role of knowledge as a contributing factor in shaping individuals' attitudes and behaviors toward electronic cigarette use.

Awareness on Electronic Cigarettes (E-cigarettes)

Awareness is the "quality or state of being aware", characterized by having knowledge and understanding that something is happening or exists (Merriam Webster, 2023). In relation to electronic cigarette use, awareness encompasses recognizing the broader implications and social aspects. It involves understanding the concerns related to electronic cigarettes' marketing and appeal to youth and the evolving regulations and policies surrounding their use. Awareness of electronic cigarette marketing tactics plays a crucial role in understanding the strategies used to promote these products. Marketers often employ various techniques to attract potential users, such as appealing flavors, sleek designs, and claims of reduced harm compared to traditional cigarettes. It is important for individuals to be aware of these marketing tactics and to critically evaluate the information presented to make informed decisions about electronic cigarette use. According to a study conducted by the University of California San Francisco in 2018, exposure to e-cigarette marketing increased the likelihood of e-cigarette use among young adults who had never used cigarettes, but not among those who had never used any tobacco products. This finding indicates that marketing tactics can influence the decisions of individuals who are not already using tobacco products. Additionally, another study found that exposure to any e-cigarette advertising may play a role in teens' decision to initiate e-cigarette and tobacco cigarette use (Padon et al., 2018). This highlights the potential impact of marketing strategies on young people and the importance of being aware of these tactics.

Furthermore, staying informed about evolving regulations for electronic cigarettes is vital due to the constantly changing regulatory landscape surrounding these products. Governments and health authorities worldwide regularly update and revise regulations to address emerging concerns and safeguard public health. Being aware of these evolving regulations helps individuals understand the legal framework under which electronic cigarettes operate, including age restrictions, product labeling requirements, marketing restrictions, and potential bans in certain areas. By staying informed about changing regulations, users and potential users of electronic cigarettes can ensure compliance with the law, make informed choices, and stay up-to-date with the latest safety guidelines.

Attitude on Electronic Cigarettes (E-cigarettes)

Attitudes are important factors that influence behavior, and this holds true for attitudes toward e-cigarettes as well. In psychology, attitude is a relatively enduring and general evaluation of an object, person, group, issue, or concept on a dimension ranging from negative to positive (Cherry, 2023). When it comes to e-cigarettes, positive attitudes are associated with increased usage, while negative attitudes act as protective factors against their use.

Positive attitudes towards e-cigarettes are often driven by perceived benefits, such as the belief that e-cigarettes are a safer alternative to traditional cigarettes or can aid in smoking cessation. Additionally, social influences, including peer or familial approval, can shape positive attitudes toward e-cigarettes. Numerous studies have consistently demonstrated a positive association between positive attitudes and increased e-cigarette usage among adolescents (Huang et al., 2018; Abu-Baker et al., 2022). On the other hand, negative attitudes serve as protective factors, dissuading adolescents from engaging in e-cigarette use (McKelvey et al., 2018). These negative attitudes can stem from an awareness of the potential health risks associated with e-cigarettes, concerns about addiction, or disapproval from peers or family members.

While studies have examined these factors among adolescents in general, there is limited research that focuses specifically on senior high school students' knowledge, awareness, and attitudes toward e-cigarettes. Senior high school level represents a critical period in adolescents' lives, characterized by unique academic demands, peer influences, and developmental changes. These factors may shape their knowledge, awareness, and attitudes toward e-cigarettes differently compared to other age groups. Despite the regulatory efforts of the government to regulate e-cigarettes, there is still a need for research to evaluate the effectiveness of said efforts and address existing gaps in knowledge. Also, the recent statistics on the prevalence of e-cigarette use among adolescents in the Philippines are limited, with the most recently available nationwide prevalence study being the Global Youth Tobacco Survey conducted in 2019 (Sese

& Guillermo, 2023), hampering the understanding of current trends and hindering the development of targeted prevention and intervention programs such as proper health education on the matter.

This study then aimed to determine the prevalence of use, knowledge, awareness, and attitude toward e-cigarettes among senior high school students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School. The results of this study are deemed to be used to address the said gaps for policymakers and public health professionals to better understand the impact of e-cigarette use among adolescents and make prevention and intervention efforts to protect public health.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess Saint Mary's University Senior High School students' prevalence, knowledge, awareness, and attitude toward electronic cigarettes by answering the following questions:

1. What is the prevalence of e-cigarettes among the respondents?
2. What is the knowledge of the respondents about the use of e-cigarettes?
3. What is the level of awareness of e-cigarettes among the respondents?
4. What is the attitude among the respondents about the use of e-cigarettes?
5. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' level of awareness towards e-cigarettes when grouped according to sex, grade level, and strand?
6. Is there a significant difference in the respondents' attitudes towards e-cigarettes when grouped according to sex, grade level, and strand?
7. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' level of awareness and attitude towards e-cigarettes?
8. What are the respondents' perceived positive and negative effects of using e-cigarettes?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized qualitative and quantitative methods. A descriptive-comparative-correlational approach was used in the quantitative section of the study. Descriptive research design was utilized to determine the prevalence of use, knowledge, awareness, and attitude on electronic cigarettes of Saint Mary's University Senior High School students. Comparative methods were used to differentiate the level of awareness and attitude among the respondents and correlational methods were used to verify the relationship of the level of awareness and attitude of the respondents towards e-cigarettes. Apart from that, qualitative responses using open-ended questions were collected to better understand the students' perceived positive and negative effects on the usage of e-cigarettes.

Participants

The study considered the entire population of Saint Mary's University Senior High School students as the respondents. However, due to the practical limitations of accessing the entire population, a quota sampling approach was adopted. In this method, a representative sample of 400 students was selected from various strands that the school offers. This sampling method ensures that the overall population of SMU Senior High School will be represented, facilitating comparisons between each strand. These strands include the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) strand, Accountancy, Business, and Management (ABM) strand, Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS) strand, Technical, Vocational and Livelihood – Information and Communications Technology (ICT), Home Economics (HE), and Arts and Design (AD) track. The respondents were further classified according to sex, grade level, and strand. A survey questionnaire was distributed physically to the selected students from each strand for data gathering.

Table 1. *Frequency and Percentage Counts of the Demographic Profile of the Respondents*

Profile Variables		N	%
Sex	Male	175	43.80%
	Female	225	56.30%
Grade Level	Grade 11	200	50.00%
	Grade 12	200	50.50%
Strand	STEM	284	71.00%
	HUMMS	52	13.00%
	ABM	36	9.00%
	AD	8	2.00%
	TVL-HE	10	2.50%
	TVL-ICT	10	2.50%
Total		400	100.00%

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents. The female respondents were composed of 225 (56.3%) and male

respondents were 175 (43.8%). The total number of students from grade 11 and grade 12 was 400, whereby 400 students voluntarily participated in this study (response rate 100%). The majority of the respondents were STEM students (n= 284, 71.0%); followed by HUMSS students (n=52, 13.0%); followed by the ABM students (n=36, 9.0%); followed by the AD students (n=8, 2.0%); followed by the TV-HE students (n=10, 2.5%) and TVL-ICT (n=10, 2.5%). In general, most of the respondents were female and from the STEM strand.

Instruments

The study used a survey questionnaire as the primary data-gathering instrument. The instrument worked to assess students' prevalence of use, knowledge, awareness, and attitude towards e-cigarettes.

It contained 3 major sections. First is the socio-demographic profile of the respondents that indicated their sex, grade level, and strand.

The second section of the questionnaire contains three parts that aimed to assess the respondents' prevalence, knowledge, awareness, and attitude on e-cigarettes. Part A, which assessed the prevalence of e-cigarette use, consisted of seven declarative statements that are answered using a dichotomous "Yes" or "No" scale. All statements were adopted from two different studies: statements one to six from the research instrument of Alanazi (2016), and statement seven from Fang et al. (2022).

Part B included 15 statements that assessed the knowledge on e-cigarettes, and was answered using a dichotomous "True" or "False" scale. Statements one to four were adapted from the research instrument of Fang et al. (2022), the modifications being that the scale used in answering was changed from a "Yes" or "No" scale to the current dichotomous "True" or "False" scale. Additionally, the sentences were modified to be declarative statements as opposed to the initial interrogative type. Meanwhile statements five to fifteen were adapted from Aghar et al. (2020). Three knowledge questions from Aghar et al. (2020) were deemed unnecessary, thus their removal. The negative statements from the study were also modified to be positive statements for a more uniform system when analyzing the data.

Part C assessed the respondents' awareness level and attitude using a Likert Scale, with 4 degrees being: 1 is Strongly Disagree, 2 is Disagree, 3 is Agree, and 4 is Strongly Agree. All declarative statements one to eight under the awareness portion were adapted from Alanazi (2016). The 13 attitude statements were then adapted from Aghar et al. (2020). Modifications were made on both portions of awareness and attitude, with the sentences being modified from interrogative sentences in the second-person point of view to declarative statements in the first-person point of view and the answer scale being modified from a dichotomous scale in the original questionnaires to a Likert scale.

Lastly, the final section of the questionnaire contains the open-ended question entailing the respondents' perception on the positive and negative effect of e-cigarette usage.

The research tool was validated by a validator, and approved by the research coordinator, and the principal.

A pilot test was conducted with 30 participants at Saint Mary's University Senior High School by simple random sampling to test the reliability of the research tool. The data collected was analyzed using the statistical program Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). Presented below is the result of the reliability test.

Table 2. Result of Reliability Test for Awareness

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardize d Items</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
.858	.873	8

Table 3. Result of Reliability Test for Attitude

<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardize d Items</i>	<i>N of Items</i>
.786	.776	13

Table 2 and 3 shows the results of the reliability statistics performed on the SPSS Software. Based on the table, the Cronbach's alpha for, awareness and attitude are 0.858, and 0.786 respectively. The internal consistency of awareness is equivalent to good ($0.9 > \alpha \geq 0.8$). Meanwhile attitude is equivalent to acceptable ($0.8 > \alpha \geq 0.7$). Since the Cronbach's alpha of the tested parameters are greater than 0.7, the questionnaire is determined to be reliable.

Procedure

The study's data gathering procedure began with the creation of a research survey questionnaire adapted from the studies of Alanazi (2016), Fang et al. (2022), and Aghar et al. (2020). The questionnaire was modified and altered to suit the significance and target respondents of the study. It underwent content validation and was checked by the research adviser, research coordinator, and validator. Then, a written permit was forwarded to the office of the principal at Saint Mary's University Senior High School to ask permission from the principal to allow the distribution of the questionnaires.

After obtaining permission, the questionnaires were distributed systematically and with clear instructions on how to fill them out. The

respondents were given sufficient time to complete the survey, after which the completed questionnaires were collected from the students. Next, data entry was performed to ensure the accuracy of the data, check for missing data, and follow up with respondents as needed to obtain complete information.

Statistical software was used to analyze the data and derive insights from it. Finally, the results were interpreted, and conclusions were drawn based on the findings, which were presented in a report that included a detailed description of the methodology, a summary of the findings, and recommendations for future research.

Data Analysis

Since the study utilize a descriptive-comparative and descriptive-correlational approach to address the research questions, the tools and techniques that is used to treat the gathered data are the following:

Frequency count and percentage distribution were used to evaluate the socio- demographic profile of the respondents and determine the prevalence of electronic cigarette use among them.

Bloom's cut-off point was used to analyze the knowledge of the respondents regarding electronic cigarettes since there is a correct and incorrect answer for each item. The observed scores on the true or false scale was computed to get the mean scores and standard deviation and were compared to the expected scores to determine whether the difference is statistically significant.

Table 4. Bloom Scale cut-off point for Knowledge

Scores (%)	Interpretation
11-15 (80%-100%)	Good
9-11(60%-79%)	Moderate
<9 (<60%)	Poor

The Mean scores and standard deviation of the 4-point Likert scale were computed to determine the level of awareness, and attitude of the respondents on electronic cigarettes. Likewise, the mean scores for each parameter were interpreted using the following systems:

Table 5. Likert Scale Interpretation on the level of awareness

Mean Score	Interpretation
3.50-4.00	Extremely Aware
2.50-3.49	Moderately Aware
1.50-2.49	Slightly Aware
1.00-1.49	Not Aware at All

Table 6. Likert Scale Interpretation on the attitude

Mean Score	Interpretation
3.50-4.00	Highly Positive Attitude
2.50-3.49	Positive Attitude
1.50-2.49	Negative Attitude
1.00-1.49	Highly Negative Attitude

Parametric statistical tools, such as independent sample t-tests and analysis of variance (ANOVA), were used to determine significant differences in the level of awareness and attitude. Independent sample t-tests were used for variables of sex and grade levels, while ANOVA was used for strands.

Pearson's R Correlation Coefficient was used to determine if there is a significant relationship between the level of awareness and attitude of the respondents on electronic cigarettes.

Thematic analysis was used to analyze the qualitative responses of the participants, such as their perceived positive and negative effects on electronic cigarette usage.

Ethical Considerations

Conflict of Interest. The researchers had no personal gain from the study and it was used mainly for academic purposes only.

Confidentiality and Data Protection. In accordance with Republic Act 10173, also known as "Data Privacy Act of 2012", the data gathered is kept confidential and can only be seen and analyzed by the researchers themselves. It was only available under the researcher's care when the data analysis was over. After which, the data will be destroyed after a certain period of time to further ensure that no data is disclosed.

Management of vulnerability. The vulnerable population, such as the underage vaping students that became participants, were not exploited or exposed since the students' names were not included in the sociodemographic profile.

Risk/Benefit Ratio. The risk that the researchers encountered was the honesty of the respondents, since vape, also known as e-cigarettes, is a sensitive topic. There was also the risk that the respondents' e-cigarette use could be exposed, which can lead to scrutiny. However,

the results of this study were a great help to other people when the study was accomplished.

Informed Consent. The researchers provided consent forms to the participants of the study indicating that the information they provided was treated with utmost confidentiality and was used for research purposes only. This was done by putting the consent forms on the front page of the questionnaire that was floated.

Terms of Reference. It is essential to acknowledge the researchers that will unequivocally hold complete ownership of the results of this study. Consequently, the researchers were rightfully entitled to claim full ownership of the outcomes of this study, guided by the advisory of the researchers' advisers. Subsequently, a hard copy of the study was submitted to the Saint Mary's University Senior High School.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the analysis, interpretation, and presentation of the findings obtained from the gathered data. The results of the analysis are presented in tabulated form and discussed regarding the study's objective which was to determine the prevalence, knowledge, awareness, and attitude on e-cigarettes among the respondents.

Descriptive of the Saint Mary's University Senior High School students according to prevalence of e-cigarette use

Table 6. *Frequency and Percentage Counts of the Prevalence of the Respondents*

Statements	Yes		No	
	n	%	n	%
I have used e-cigarettes at least once during my lifetime.	206	51.50%	194	48.50%
I have used e-cigarettes in the last month.	142	35.00%	258	65.00%
I intend to use e-cigarettes in the next year.	84	21.00%	316	79.00%
I have friends who have tried e-cigarettes.	312	78.00%	88	22.00%
I have parents who have used e-cigarettes.	87	21.80%	313	78.20%
I have siblings who have used e-cigarettes.	115	28.70%	285	71.30%
I have roommates who have used e-cigarettes.	101	25.20%	299	74.80%

Table 6 shows the prevalence of e-cigarette use among senior high school students at Saint Mary's University Senior High School. Half of the respondents (51.5%), answered "yes" to having used e-cigarettes at least once during their lifetime. Whilst 312 respondents (78%) have friends that use e-cigarettes.

With the high percentage of respondents (78%) stating that they have friends who use e-cigarettes, it can be presumed that peers are likely to have influenced the use of more than half of the respondents (51.5%), as they affect the popularity of e-cigarettes. Thus, they can influence one's decision to try, use, or have continual usage of e-cigarettes.

Studies by Fang et al. (2022), Wang et al. (2022), and Cheng et al. (2023) agree with the finding that e-cigarette use can be influenced by peers. Also, Alfaraj et al. (2019) agree, as they determined that the popularity of e-cigarettes could be due to the immense advertising by friends and relatives. Yet it is also contradicting because whilst they found that relatives can contribute to its popularity, only a few respondents stated having relatives who use e-cigarettes (parents, 21.8%; siblings, 28.7%).

Knowledge of Saint Mary's University Senior High School students on E- cigarette

Table 7 shows the respondents' knowledge of e-cigarettes. As seen from the table, most of the respondents (96.25%) correctly answered that e-cigarettes contain nicotine, yet only 267 respondents (66.8%) accurately answered that e-cigarettes are tobacco products. On the other hand, a majority of the health-related questions about the harmful effects and associations of e-cigarettes garnered high scores (carcinogenic properties, 84.3%; addiction, 96%; different flavoring, 80.3%; e-cigarette liquid, lung cancer, 92%; impaired lung and heart function, 95.5%; second-hand smoking, 91.3%; fetal development, 94%; aerosol, 90.8; harmful lung conditions, 95.5%). Despite this, some respondents (31.5%) falsely believed that e-cigarettes were harmless.

Though it is well established among the respondents that e-cigarettes contain nicotine, some are still unaware that these devices are tobacco products. This suggests that there may be a potential lack of information among the students about the regulatory classifications of e-cigarettes. Nicotine is a highly addictive substance found in tobacco, and while e-cigarettes may not contain tobacco in the traditional sense, they are often classified as tobacco products due to their association with nicotine and their potential health risks (CDC, 2023).

Additionally, while students know that e-cigarettes are related to harmful health impacts and diseases yet still consider them harmless or less harmful than cigarettes, this suggests that there could be a belief system or perception within them that dismisses the effects of usage. These perceptions could be attributed to misinformation or lack thereof, marketing influences, social norms and peer influence, and even personal experience. Altogether, it could even be suggested that because students are unaware that e-cigarettes are tobacco products, several are led to believe such products can be harmless.

Table 7. Score of the Respondents in the Knowledge Section (n=400)

Statements	Expected Ideal Response	Correct	
		n	%
1. E-cigarettes contain nicotine.	True	385	96.25%
2. E-cigarettes are tobacco products.	True	267	66.80%
3. E-cigarettes are carcinogenic.	True	337	84.30%
4. E-cigarettes are addictive.	True	384	96.00%
5. Some flavors of E-cigarettes are more harmful than others.	True	321	80.30%
6. Swallowing the liquid in E-cigarettes accidentally can cause poisoning that is potentially fatal.	False	341	85.30%
7. E-cigarettes are associated with lung cancer.	True	368	92.00%
8. E-cigarettes impair lung and heart functions.	True	382	95.50%
9. E-cigarettes contribute to second hand smoking.	True	365	91.30%
10. E-cigarettes can have an effect on fetal development.	True	376	94.00%
11. Harmful flavorings and toxins are found in the E-cigarette aerosol.	True	363	90.80%
12. E-cigarettes are harmless.	False	274	68.50%
13. Some components of the liquid found in E- cigarettes can cause harmful lung conditions.	True	382	95.50%
14. E-cigarettes are suitable for pregnant women.	False	359	89.80%
15. E-cigarettes are suitable for children.	False	352	88.00%

Contrastingly, the study of Aghar et al. (2020), from which the knowledge questions were adapted, produced opposite results. Their results show that more than half of their respondents showed a lack of knowledge concerning e-cigarettes. For example, the lack of knowledge concerning the association of usage with lung cancer and impaired lung and heart function; 54.4% and 50.9%, respectively as compared to the results of this study which are 92% and 95.5%, respectively. With these results in mind, their study goes on to emphasize that “those who are more knowledgeable about EC use would also know more about its potential harms.” Therefore, it contradicts the results of this study, wherein respondents affirmed that e-cigarette usage has health implications yet falsely believe it to be harmless still. Furthermore, another study by Acosta (2022) revealed that the majority of the respondents were knowledgeable about some of the harmful effects of e-cigarettes on their overall health, but a small percentage (5.4%) of respondents were unaware of the addictive nature of nicotine in e-cigarettes. These findings align with the observation from Aghar et al. (2020) that knowledge about e-cigarettes and their potential health harms does not necessarily translate into accurate risk perception.

Table 8. Level of knowledge of the respondents on e-cigarette

Category	n	%
Good knowledge	340	85.00%
Moderate knowledge	44	11.00%
Poor knowledge	16	4.00%

Legend: Good knowledge (11-15 correct answers), Moderate knowledge (9-10 correct answers), Poor knowledge (9 correct answers and below)

Table 8 presents data on respondents' knowledge of e-cigarettes. The majority of respondents (85%) demonstrated good knowledge about e-cigarettes, while a smaller group (4%) exhibited poor knowledge, and a moderate knowledge level was observed in 11% of the respondents. The high prevalence of good knowledge suggests that the majority of the respondents had a good understanding of e-cigarettes. This implies that most respondents are likely aware of both the potential health risks and benefits of e-cigarettes, and could make informed decisions about their use. Similarly, a study by Abo-Elkheir and Sobh (2016) found that higher knowledge led to better attitudes and practices, potentially indicating that knowing more about e-cigarettes promotes responsible use or avoidance.

Level of awareness on e-cigarette among Saint Mary's University Senior High School students.

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics of the Level of Awareness of the Respondents

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I have heard of electronic cigarettes (E- cigarette).	3.45	0.89	Moderately aware
2. I am aware that e-cigarettes are a nicotine delivery system.	3.40	0.85	Moderately aware
3. I am aware that an e-cigarette is an appliance that vaporizes nicotine.	3.34	0.83	Moderately aware
4. I am aware that an e-cigarette can be inhaled with different additives (i.e., Nicotine).	3.37	0.84	Moderately aware
5. I am aware that an e-cigarette can be inhaled with different flavors (i.e., Peach).	3.45	0.80	Moderately aware
6. I am aware that there is no combustion in an e- cigarette.	2.57	0.93	Moderately aware
7. I am aware that there is no carbon monoxide in an e-cigarette.	2.53	0.93	Moderately aware
8. I am aware that an e-cigarette is not currently regulated by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA).	2.89	0.96	Moderately aware
Mean Awareness	3.13	0.64	Moderately aware

Legend: Extremely aware (3.50-4.00), Moderately aware (2.50-3.49), Slightly aware (1.50- 2.49), Not aware at all (1.00-1.49)

Table 9 shows the mean level of awareness of students towards e-cigarettes. As indicated in the table, there are two statements that gathered the highest mean score. The statements “I have heard of electronic cigarettes (E-cigarette)” and “I am aware that an e-cigarette can be inhaled with different flavors” both have a mean score of 3.45. Furthermore, the overall level of awareness of students on e-cigarettes are moderate (Mean =3.13; SD=0.64). This implies that the respondents have a basic understanding of e-cigarettes, including their existence and the presence of flavored options. Likewise, the investigation by Daniluk et al. (2018) lends support to these findings, as their participants demonstrated an understanding of the chemical composition of substances found in e-cigarettes.

Table 10. Comparison of the Level of Awareness in Terms of Sex

Level of Awareness	Male		Female		t(400)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
	3.15	0.70	3.11	0.60	0.52	0.60

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Table 10 presents the difference in the level of awareness among the respondents when grouped according to sex. The male respondents had a mean awareness of 3.15, while the females had 3.11, and the results of the analysis show that there is no significant difference in the level of awareness ($t=.52$; $p=.60$) when grouped according to sex. Moreover, the respective mean level of awareness of both sexes also indicates that they are moderately aware of e-cigarettes.

When comparing said means, males seem to have a higher level of awareness than females, but not to a significant degree, even with the minimal difference observed. This implies that males’ higher level of awareness suggests that it could be due to their exposure to e-cigarettes, and likewise cigarette and tobacco products, related information as per their usage.

Cheah et al. (2019) suggest this could be due to men being more likely to use e-cigarettes than women (Tehrani et al., 2022; Kurdi et al., 2021). In line with the difference in awareness level, a cross-sectional analysis of Global Adult Tobacco Survey (GATS) data from 14 countries during the years 2011–2017 likewise found that females were less aware of e-cigarettes (Kundu et al., 2019). This tendency of higher male awareness of e-cigarettes was also observed in several other studies (Cheah et al., 2019).

Table 11. Comparison of the Level of Awareness in Terms of Grade Level

Level of Awareness	Grade 11		Grade 12		t(400)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
	3.03	0.64	3.22	0.64	-2.84*	0.01

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Table 11 shows the difference in the level of awareness among respondents when grouped according to grade level. The grade 11 students have a mean level of awareness of 3.03 and the grade 12 students have a mean level of awareness of 3.22, which implies that both grade levels are moderately aware of e-cigarettes. Obtaining the p-value of 0.01, it was determined that there is a significant difference in the level of awareness ($t = -2.84$; $p = .01$) of the respondents towards e-cigarettes when grouped according to grade level.

The difference in mean awareness levels may be attributed to the higher percentage of users among grade 12 students, for they are more exposed to information regarding e-cigarette usage. This finding agrees with Rhode et al. (2018), who found that older students generally have higher levels of awareness. However, Cheah, Y. K. et al. (2019) contradict this, showing that awareness was highest among 11th graders compared to 12th graders.

Table 12. Comparison of the Level of Awareness of the Respondents in Terms of Strand

Factors	Strands	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Level of Awareness	STEM	3.15	0.67	0.74	0.60
	HUMMS	3.08	0.63		
	ABM	3.14	0.43		
	AD	3.19	0.68		
	TVL-HE	2.85	0.63		
	TVL-ICT	2.90	0.64		

*Not Significant ($p>0.05$)

Table 12 shows the results of an analysis of variance examining the awareness of electronic cigarettes among students when grouped according to strands. The analysis indicates that there is no significant difference in the level of awareness ($F = .74$; $p > 0.05$) of electronic cigarettes among students from these diverse academic strands. The p-value of 0.60 suggests that there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, implying that the differences observed in awareness levels are not statistically significant. This means that, regardless of the academic strand, students appear to have similar levels of awareness regarding electronic cigarettes.

The absence of a significant difference in awareness levels across different strands implies that students from different academic strands are equally informed or uninformed, regardless of their field of study. Likewise, a study by Oliveira et al. (2018) concluded that there was no statistical significance in the course differences among undergraduates in their awareness of similar health-related topics.

Attitude on e-cigarette among Saint Mary’s University Senior High School students

Table 13. Descriptive Statistics of the Attitude of the Respondents

Statements	Mean	SD	Description
1. I think E-cigarettes should be recommended nonsmoker.	1.59	0.96	Negative Attitude
2. I think E-cigarettes are harmful for health.	3.31	0.95	Positive Attitude
3. I think the use of E-cigarettes should be allowed in places that do not allow smoking.	1.67	0.98	Negative Attitude
4. I think I would consider someone who uses E-cigarettes a smoker.	2.84	1.00	Positive Attitude
5. I think the use of E-cigarettes can lead to reliance.	2.71	0.94	Positive Attitude
6. I think that the government should regulate the use of E-cigarettes.	2.37	1.07	Negative Attitude
7. I think it is acceptable to experiment with E-cigarettes for pleasure.	2.20	1.02	Negative Attitude
8. I think it is more comfortable to use or openly talk about smoking E-cigarettes, compared to cigarettes.	2.57	1.03	Positive Attitude
9. I think it is more socially acceptable to smoke E-cigarettes, compared to cigarettes.	2.52	1.00	Positive Attitude
10. I think E-cigarettes should be used as a replacement for regular cigarettes.	2.40	1.02	Negative Attitude
11. I think using E-cigarettes would be an effective way to help in smoking cessation.	2.36	0.98	Negative Attitude
12. I think it is acceptable to use E-cigarettes as a smoking cessation method.	2.34	0.96	Negative Attitude
13. I think E-cigarettes can help people cut down on cigarettes or quit smoking.	2.41	1.03	Negative Attitude
Mean Attitude	2.41	0.63	Negative Attitude

Legend: Highly Positive Attitude (3.50-4.00), Positive Attitude (2.50-3.49), Negative Attitude (1.50-2.49), Highly Negative Attitude (1.00-1.49)

Table 13 presents data on respondents' attitudes towards e-cigarettes. The majority of respondents hold a negative view of e-cigarettes, as evidenced by the overall mean attitude of 2.41 falling within the "negative attitude" range (mean = 2.41). However, this negativity isn't absolute. Highlighted statements like "It's more comfortable to use or talk about e-cigarettes compared to cigarettes" (mean = 2.57) and "E-cigarettes should be used as a replacement for regular cigarettes" (mean = 2.40) all fall within the "positive attitude" range. These findings suggest that while most people hold a negative view of e-cigarettes due to health concerns and their potential as a gateway to smoking, especially young people, some see them as a less harmful or more socially acceptable alternative to traditional cigarettes. A similar mixed opinion was found in a 2022 study by Abu Baker et al. among adolescents

Table 14. Comparison of the Attitude in Terms of Sex

Level of Awareness	Male		Female		t(400)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
	2.48	0.70	2.35	0.56	2.18*	0.03

*Not Significant (p>0.05)

The findings suggest that there is a significant difference in the level of attitude among the respondents when grouped according to sex. Considering the respective mean attitudes, both females and males are implied to have a negative attitude towards e- cigarettes, as seen in the interpretation scale.

Comparing said means, the female respondents’ mean attitude was lower than the male respondents’, implying that they have at least a more negative attitude towards e- cigarettes than males do. This could be due to the difference in representation, as e-cigarettes and even cigarette usage as such are viewed as more taboo for women than men. Subsequently, it may also attest to why males tend to have a higher usage rate than females (Tehrani et al., 2022; Kurdi et al., 2021).

The implication of e-cigarette use being more taboo for women has also been suggested by Palmes et al. (2021) in their study concerning e-cigarette use among undergraduate nursing students in an urban university in the Philippines. With a predominantly female sample size (89.3%), they stated that since e-cigarettes are generally taboo for females, female participants may consciously deny knowing about e-cigarettes and continue to hold an opposing attitude towards usage to avoid retribution. Although the findings of Shilco et al. (2020) on adolescents’ knowledge and attitudes found that there were no significant sex differences detected among the results analyzed from their findings, there were significant differences found in sex in the study of Palmes et al. (2021). Additionally, Alduraywishi et al. (2023), a study on 1st year college students’ knowledge and attitudes toward e-cigarettes in Saudi Arabia, found that more female participants expressed disapproval. There was also a prevalence of female participants showing a protective effect, with a negative attitude and strong disagreement towards e-cigarettes, while male smokers have a lowered harm perception of e-cigarettes.

Table 15. Comparison of the Attitude in Terms of Grade Level

Level of Awareness	Grade 11		Grade 12		t(400)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
	2.28	0.63	2.54	0.60	-4.16*	0.00

*Not Significant (p>0.05)

Table 15 presents the difference in the level of attitude among the respondents when grouped according to grade level. The grade 11 students garnered a mean attitude of 2.28, which classifies them as having a negative attitude towards e-cigarettes. The grade 12

students, in contrast, had a mean attitude score of 2.54, indicating that they had a positive attitude towards e-cigarettes. Accordingly, the findings indicate a significant difference in attitude when grouped by grade level.

In comparison, the 11th graders showed a more negative attitude than the 12th graders. Several reasons for this could be the difference in exposure and access. Since 12th graders are closer to the legal age of usage and purchasing, it would be reasonable to consider that some have already been exposed, and likewise influenced, by friends and fellow classmates who are users.

Regarding access, the matter of negligent selling by e-cigarette buyers has also allowed the youth to purchase such items with unmonitored access (Sese & Guillermo, 2023; Philippine Legislators' Committee on Population and Development [PLCPD], 2021).

Table 16. Comparison of the Attitude of the Respondents in Terms of Strand

Factors	Strands	Mean	SD	F-value	p-value
Attitude	STEM	2.35	0.63	0.91	0.09
	HUMSS	2.46	0.61		
	ABM	2.53	0.56		
	AD	2.81	0.59		
	TVL-HE	2.67	0.57		
	TVL-ICT	2.57	0.80		

*Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 16 shows the results of an analysis examining the significant difference in the attitudes of respondents toward e-cigarettes when grouped according to their academic strands. It shows that there is no statistically significant difference in the attitudes of the respondents toward e-cigarettes ($F = 1.91$; $p > 0.05$) across these different academic strands. The average attitudes towards e-cigarettes differed slightly across academic tracks, with students in "AD" having the most positive views ($M = 2.81$) and "STEM" students having the least favorable views ($M = 2.35$). However, statistically speaking, these variations weren't significant ($F = 1.91$; $p > 0.05$).

This suggests that, despite some minor differences, students from different academic backgrounds held broadly similar views on e-cigarettes. Contrastingly, a study by Lozano et al. (2015) found that the attitudes of students towards electronic cigarettes from different courses have shown a significant difference.

Relationship of the level of awareness and attitude on e-cigarette among Saint Mary's University Senior High School students

Table 17. Correlation between Level of Awareness and Attitude

	Pearson's r	p-value	QD
Level of Awareness	0.39*	0.00	Moderately Low Correlation
Attitude			

Legend: Pearson r / Qualitative Description; +0.80 – +0.99 / Very High Correlation; +0.60 – +0.79 / Moderately High Correlation; +0.40 – +0.59 / High Correlation; +0.20 – +0.39 / Moderately Low Correlation; +0.01 – +0.19 / Very Low Correlation; *Not Significant ($p > 0.05$)

Table 17 shows the analysis of Pearson's correlation coefficient (r) between the level of awareness and the attitude of the students towards e-cigarettes, which yielded a positive value of 0.39. This positive value suggests that as the level of awareness among the students' increases, there is a corresponding increase in their attitude towards e-cigarettes.

However, it's important to note that the magnitude of the correlation, as indicated by Pearson's r, was relatively modest at 0.39. The statistical significance of this correlation was confirmed with a two-tailed significance (Sig.) value of 0.00, which is less than the conventional significance level of 0.05. This also suggests that the relationship between the level of awareness and the level of attitude is not particularly strong. It means that the level of awareness does not strongly affect the level of attitude in any way. Furthermore, since this study is relatively new to the community, the study related to the variables is very limited. Thus, there is no study found to relate to this certain table.

Perceive positive and negative effects on e-cigarette among Saint Mary's University Senior High School students

Table 18 shows the positive perceptions of e-cigarettes among 400 respondents. The positive perceptions table shows that the most common positive perception of e-cigarettes is that they provide pleasure and emotional benefits, such as relaxation and stress relief, with 119 (29.75%). The statement "none" was reported by 83 (20.75%) respondents. This is followed by the perception that e-cigarettes are less harmful compared to traditional cigarettes, with 59 (14.75%) respondents. 50 (12.50%) respondents also reported using e-cigarettes as a way to quit smoking cigarettes.

Respondents suggested that e-cigarettes can provide a way to enjoy the act of smoking without the harmful effects of traditional cigarettes. Additionally, some mentioned using e-cigarettes as a coping mechanism for stress or anxiety. One of the positive themes was the perception that e-cigarettes can serve as an alternative to smoking. Respondents mentioned using e-cigarettes to quit smoking or reduce their traditional cigarette consumption in favor of e-cigarettes. This suggests that, for some, e-cigarettes have potential harm reduction benefits. A number of respondents mentioned the lower environmental impact of e-cigarettes compared to traditional

cigarettes. This indicates that some individuals are considering e-cigarettes as a more environmentally friendly option, possibly due to reduced secondhand smoke and cigarette butt litter.

Table 18. *Perceived Positive Effects on E-cigarettes (N=400)*

<i>Positive Effects</i>	<i>Sample Responses</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Pleasure and emotional factors	It gives a sense of euphoria for the user and helps them calm down Stress reliever It doesn't affect you as much as normal cigarettes do. Less harmful	119	29.75%
None	None	83	20.75%
Comparison to traditional cigarettes	It doesn't affect you as much as normal cigarettes do. Less harmful.	59	14.75%
Blank		54	13.50%
Alternative	A good substitute for cigarettes. Can help someone quit smoking	50	12.50%
Cost, advertisement, and accessibility	Can make you feel cool It is more acceptable to use e-cigarettes than traditional cigarettes	16	4.00%
Peer influence and social stigma	Can make you feel cool. It is more acceptable to use e- cigarettes than regular cigarettes.	5	1.25%
Addictive	Can be addictive	5	1.25%
Environmental impact	It does not lead to so much garbage disposal unlike cigarette sticks which are one-time use only.	5	1.25%
Not aware	I am not that aware when it comes to e- cigarettes	4	14.50%

The present findings regarding the perceived positive effects of e-cigarette use align with the observations of Romijnders et al. (2018) in their narrative literature review. Their work suggests that the appeal of e-cigarettes is multifaceted, driven by perceived benefits such as enhanced taste and reduced harmfulness, alongside potential uses as a smoking cessation tool and social influence from peers who vape.

Table 19. *Perceived Negative Effects on E-cigarettes (N=400)*

<i>Negative effects</i>	<i>Sample Responses</i>	<i>n</i>	<i>%</i>
Health and Safety	Bad for your health. Can destroy our health and affect others by smelling the smoke of e-cigarettes. Lung and heart disease.	223	55.75%
Addiction	Addicting and can cause health problems that can lead to death Leads to addiction	74	18.50%
Cost and accessibility	Students who are underage use e- cigarettes. E-cigarettes can be expensive yet long lasting.	55	13.75%
Comparison to traditional cigarettes	It has the same bad effects as traditional cigarettes but advertise as a better alternative.	15	3.75%
None	None	13	2.25%
Not aware	I don't know because I'm not using either e-cigarettes or cigarettes.	10	2.50%
		7	1.75%
Environmental impact	There are many negative effects of E- cigarettes it contributes our air pollution, it can harm our living and it is addicting	3	0.75%

The negative perception table shows that the most common negative perception of e- cigarettes is that they are addictive and harmful to health, with 74 (18.50%) and 223 (55.75%) respondents, respectively. The perception that e-cigarettes are expensive and accessible was raised by 55 (13.75%) respondents.

Health and safety emerged as the most prevalent theme, with concerns about the potential negative health effects of e-cigarettes being widely expressed. Addiction was closely related to health and safety concerns, as respondents emphasized the addictive nature of e-cigarettes and the possibility of addiction even for those who never smoked traditional cigarettes. Cost and accessibility were also raised as concerns. Some respondents argued that e-cigarettes can be expensive, while others were worried about their easy availability, even to minors. Peer influence and social stigma were less prominent but still present themes. Respondents expressed concerns about the growing popularity of e- cigarettes among young people, potentially leading to increased smoking rates. They also raised concerns about marketing practices that make e-cigarettes appear more socially acceptable than traditional cigarettes.

The findings concerning the perceived negative effects of e-cigarette use in Table 20 receive strong support from the systematic review by Sharma et al. (2021), which investigated adolescents' health perceptions of e-cigarettes. Their analysis confirms that adolescents perceive e-cigarettes as less harmful than traditional cigarettes yet simultaneously harbor concerns about potential health risks like addiction and lung damage. Notably, both the thematic analysis of our study and the cited systematic review highlight the influence of external factors, including peer influence and marketing, on shaping adolescents' e-cigarette perceptions.

Conclusions

E-cigarette usage is prevalent among senior high school students, with a significant percentage having tried them. Most students demonstrate good knowledge about e-cigarettes, and on average, they exhibit a moderately aware level of understanding. However, their overall attitude is negative, implying a general lack of intention to use e-cigarettes. Significant differences in awareness were observed primarily among grade levels, with grade 12 students displaying higher awareness. No significant differences were found based on sex or academic strand. In terms of attitude, both grade level and sex prove to be influential factors, with grade 12 students and males showing more positive attitudes, indicating a higher likelihood of e-cigarette usage in these groups. These findings align with the positive correlation found between the level of awareness and attitude, indicating that increased awareness may lead to a greater tendency for e-cigarette usage. Concerning the perceived impacts, students hold diverse perceptions of e-cigarettes, with certain students acknowledging positive effects such as pleasure and relaxation, while others express concerns about addiction and health risks.

E-cigarette use may continue to see a trend as it becomes more widespread among adolescents. In hopes of addressing the current usage of e-cigarettes by youth and even the possible trend, several recommendations can be used to improve this study.

When replicating or adapting the study, it is recommended that it be conducted in an educational institution. For the manner of conducting the survey, respondents' safety and anonymity should be constantly prioritized and assured. As the reliability of the respondents' answers may be unsure, possibly due to fear of implication in usage as some are minors, it is recommended to take proper measures and go about with utmost discretion to assure the respondents of their anonymity and safety in answering.

For the variables, retain the variables "sex," "grade level" (year level for higher education), and "strand" (course or specialty for higher education). Meanwhile, the variable "e-cigarette use" can be added, categorizing respondents accordingly: never used, ever user, current user, former user. The study by Wang et al. (2016) provided several detailed definitions of what these categories entail and which could be adapted for certain studies. By adding this variable, it can be determined whether or not personal e-cigarette use influences one's knowledge, awareness, and attitude toward e-cigarettes.

For prevalence, it is advisable to utilize an entire population instead of simply computing the sample size to better determine the prevalence on a larger scale. Thereafter, grouping all measuring parameters according to the socio-demographic profile would give a better representation of the definite number of respondents that have never used, have used occasionally, are currently using, and were former users.

For further recommendations in the method of the study, although this study focused mainly on gaining information on adolescents' insights regarding usage, it is recommended to study further the factors and covariates that could warrant usage, i.e., having friends who use e-cigarettes can increase the likelihood of usage. Also, looking further into the external factors and methods of how adolescents become influenced, such as advertisements and exposure to social media, can help define the root of the issue deeper and help give accountability to those responsible. In consequence, more insights into the underlying social processes resulting in the psychology and behavior of e-cigarette use by adolescents can be gained.

Lastly, for the output of this study, the findings can be used to develop targeted educational campaigns based on research findings to inform adolescents of the risks and address their specific concerns.

For educational institutions and the youth, effective engagement can be done through community centers, online platforms, and especially schools by creating effective campaigns that resonate with the youth. Evidence-based e-cigarette prevention programs can be integrated into the curriculum, such as in values formation subjects like the Homeroom Guidance Program (HGP). Consequently, interactive materials and activities, like scenario-based learning, that address the specific concerns and motivations of adolescents can be used to engage students and enhance their understanding of the consequences of e-cigarette use.

For the government, regular assessment of the effectiveness of prevention programs can be done using research-based evaluation methods, subsequently adapting and refining said strategies to ensure their relevance and impact. This can include collaborating with medical associations, public health agencies, and non-profit organizations dedicated to health promotion in the dissemination of research findings.

For future researchers, regularly updating educational materials and campaigns to reflect the latest findings and ensuring accuracy will keep the public informed about ongoing research developments in the field of e-cigarettes.

By incorporating our research findings into these strategies, awareness and prevention initiatives can be more targeted, evidence-based, and impactful in deterring adolescents from engaging in e-cigarette use.

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